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Analysis of the Identity Construction and Persuasion Language in the Speeches of Putin and Zelensky during the on-going Russo-Ukrainian War

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Abstract

This study aims at analysing, in a comparative manner, the speeches of the Russian President, Vladimir Putin and the Ukrainian President, Volodymyr Zelensky as used during the Russo-Ukrainian war. To achieve the objectives, the research adopted the mixed method for data collection, analysis, interpretation, and discussion of findings. A purposive sampling was used to select the speeches – two from each of the Presidents. This study employed the Critical Discourse Analysis theory as propounded by Fairclough (2013) and Aristotle's persuasive strategies of pathos, ethos, and logos (1939) as the analytical frameworks. The data gleaned from the speeches were categorized under the use of the pronouns "we" versus "they", "our" versus "you", etc. and the use of the different types of appeals. Results revealed that both Vladimir Putin and Volodymyr Zelensky make use of pronouns to create a sense of patriotism, bravery, otherness, and togetherness. However, the findings portray that unlike Putin, Zelensky uses the pronoun "we" and "us" in a more conciliatory and condescending manner. As regards the use of the different kinds of appeals, the findings revealed that Putin had recourse to logical appeals as he kept on justifying his option for war. On the other hand, Zelensky made more of emotional appeals especially when he paints the gory picture of the effects of the ongoing war between Russia and Ukraine. Pedagogical implications of the study were made to curriculum designers and suggestions for further studies were also made.

Keywords: Identity construction, Critical Discourse analysis, Russo-Ukrainian war, Aristotle's rhetoric

1. Introduction

Language plays a crucial role in the course and escalation of wars, influencing public perception and either promoting peaceful resolutions or fuelling conflicts. The use of language during wartime can have significant consequences, as it shapes narratives and ideologies. Language, in this context, refers to the communication system comprising words, expressions, and discourse used by individuals and groups involved in the conflict.

Numerous studies have underscored the significant impact of language on the course and accentuation of wars. Matthew Levinger (2007) found that propaganda played a crucial

role in the Rwandan genocide, where dehumanizing language contributed to inciting violence against Tutsis. Alex Housen's study (2011) highlighted how nationalist language employed by political leaders escalated conflicts in Bosnia and Herzegovina. These studies demonstrate that language can both fuel and shape the trajectory of wars, making it essential to critically examine the language used by political leaders during conflicts.

To conduct this research, a corpus of speeches, interviews, and public statements by Putin and Zelensky related to the Russo-Ukraine war is meticulously analysed using critical discourse analysis methodology. The analysis primarily focusses on identifying recurrent patterns in their language usage, exploring the persuasive strategies employed, and unravelling how they construct their respective visions of the conflict. By examining their linguistic choices, this study endeavours to enhance our understanding of how language is wielded within the context of war, with a specific emphasis on the Russo-Ukraine conflict.

Language is a powerful tool in shaping attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours, especially in the context of conflicts. Previous research has emphasized the significance of discourse analysis in understanding conflicts and the role of language in legitimizing or delegitimizing actions (Fairclough, 2015; Hutchinson & Williams, 2019; Wodak, 2015). However, there is a notable research gap regarding the specific analysis of pronoun usage in the discourse of leaders involved in the Russian-Ukraine war. This study aims to address this gap by conducting a comparative critical discourse analysis of the speeches delivered by Russian President Vladimir Putin and Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelensky during the Russo-Ukrainian war. The focus will be on examining the utilization of pronouns and other persuasive strategies employed by the leaders to shape public opinion and justify their actions.

Political language deals with the use of power to organize people's mind and opinion. It is an instrument used to control the society in general. Speech heard by a lot of people, every person has different interpretations that can influence the success of the candidates. Political speech can be seen as a means of establishing and maintaining social relationships, expressing feelings, and selling ideas, policies and programmes in any society. In pragmatics aspect, this means Speech Act Theory; speech act performed by particular word often depends on the speaker's intention and the context in which the word uttered.

Dehumanization is a commonly observed tactic in wars, achieved through language that portrays the opponent as less than human. This tactic justifies violence and aggression, as it creates a perception that the targeted group is unworthy of empathy or protection. For instance, during the Rwandan genocide, the Hutu radio station referred to Tutsis as "cockroaches," fuelling violence against them. Similarly, Jews were dehumanized as "rats" or "parasites" during the Holocaust, enabling the justification of horrific acts. Such language devalues the opponent, making it easier to rationalize violence against them (Jones, 2006).

Nationalism is another linguistic factor that can contribute to the course or escalation of wars. When political leaders employ language that emphasizes national pride and superiority, conflicts with other nations can arise. Adolf Hitler's use of nationalist

language, portraying the German people as superior and justifying the need for territorial expansion, played a significant role in the escalation of World War II (Mosse, 1975).

Propaganda serves as a powerful linguistic tool during wars, promoting specific ideologies and viewpoints. In times of conflict, propaganda is used to demonize the enemy, rally support for the war effort, and manipulate public opinion. The U.S. government, during World War II, employed propaganda to depict the Japanese as barbaric and subhuman, creating a dehumanizing narrative that justified their mistreatment (Sloan, 2008). Similarly, during the Vietnam War, propaganda portrayed the Vietnamese as communists threatening American democracy, further fuelling support for the conflict.

The term political discourse can refer in a number of ways to a range of different types of talk or text. Also, it is used to refer to a type of discourse which is a political production—a speech, debate, political interview, policy document, and so on (Van Dijk, 1997; Fairclough and Fairclough 2012). In a similar vein, Cicero (1971) claims that due to the persuasive nature of political language, it has been equated with the term “rhetoric” because the original use of the term was to describe particular forms of persuasion within political assemblies. It is worth mentioning that rhetorical studies of political discourse are directed to capture rhetorical and argumentation procedures, their identification, and their persuasive effects. Hence, the “political” becomes one genre for the display of rhetorical forms of persuasion or performance, rather than an analysis of the ways in which linguistic selection and production not only derives from language theory, but also suggests a definition of what is political. More accurately, ‘political discourse’ refers to the study of political language where the focus is on aspects of language structure as it constitutes and exhibits specific political functions. Many discourse analysts suggested that the study of political language may be regarded as “a sub discipline between linguistics and political science” (Wodak 2011, p. 6).

This research is particularly relevant given the ongoing conflict and its implications for international relations. By scrutinizing the linguistic strategies of Putin and Zelensky, this study seeks to shed light on how language is instrumentalised to justify and legitimize military actions. The findings offer valuable insights for conflict resolution initiatives and provide a deeper comprehension of the influential role of language in shaping attitudes and beliefs during times of conflict.

The work is subdivided as follows: (1) Introduction, (2) Literature Review (3) Methodology, (4) Discussion, and (5) Conclusion. These are taken in turn below.

2. Review of Literature

The comparative study of Putin and Zelensky's speeches at the Russo-Ukraine war offers valuable insights into their discursive practices and rhetorical strategies. Through a linguistic perspective, we can explore the ways in which language is employed to justify military actions, mobilize support, and construct national identities. This analysis sheds light on the similarities and differences in the discursive approaches of the two leaders,

providing a nuanced understanding of their communication strategies during the conflict. The first part of this section reviews a number of concepts related to this study.

2.1 Power and Ideology in Discourse

Power and ideology play crucial roles in discourse, influencing the construction of meaning and the negotiation of social reality. Power refers to the ability to influence and control others, and it is exercised through language in various social and political contexts (Fairclough, 1995). Language is a key tool for those in power to maintain their dominance and shape public opinion (Van Dijk, 2009). Ideology, on the other hand, refers to a system of beliefs, values, and norms that shape individuals' understanding of the world and their actions within it (Fairclough, 2003).

In political conflicts, discourse becomes a battleground for power struggles and the dissemination of competing ideologies. Political leaders strategically use language to construct and reinforce their own identities, as well as to construct and demonize the "other" (Chilton, 2004).

2.2 National Identity and Collective Belonging

National identity and collective belonging play a pivotal role in political conflicts, where language is a powerful means for constructing and reinforcing these identities. Political leaders strategically employ discursive strategies to evoke patriotism, cultural values, and historical narratives that shape the collective identity of their respective nations (Chilton, 2004). Through the use of language, leaders seek to foster a sense of belonging among their supporters, while also creating a distinct separation from the perceived "other" (Billig, 1995).

In the context of the Russo-Ukraine war, the speeches of Putin and Zelensky offer valuable insights into how national identity and collective belonging are constructed and mobilized. By analysing their language use, rhetorical devices, and narrative framing, researchers can unravel the discursive techniques employed to shape the collective identity of their nations. These techniques may include the invocation of shared history, cultural symbols, and narratives that emphasize the unique characteristics and virtues of their respective countries (Machin & Mayr, 2012).

Furthermore, studying the discursive practices of Putin and Zelensky allows for an exploration of how these leaders position their nations in relation to the conflict. They may employ language to reinforce a sense of unity, resilience, and determination among their citizens, while also portraying the adversary as a threat to national values and interests (Charteris-Black, 2011).

2.3 Emotion and Persuasion in Political Discourse

Emotional appeals and persuasive language play a crucial role in political discourse, particularly in times of conflict. Political leaders strategically employ emotional rhetoric to evoke specific responses and mobilize public support (Charteris-Black, 2011). Emotions such as fear, anger, and solidarity can be strategically harnessed to shape public opinion, justify particular actions, and galvanize the populace (Wodak & Meyer, 2016).

In the context of the Russo-Ukraine war, analysing the emotional appeals and persuasive strategies utilized by Putin and Zelensky in their speeches provides valuable insights into how language is used to sway public sentiment and garner support for their respective positions. By examining the emotional dimensions of their discourses, researchers can unravel the discursive techniques employed to shape public opinion, evoke empathy, and motivate action (Phillipson, 2008).

2.4 Aristotelian Rhetoric as Persuasive strategies

Persuasion is fundamental and peculiar to the speech of politicians and influencers. This is because politicians deploy means to persuade the audience to support and identify with the opinion of interest. Nelson (2004) asserted that persuasive communication is aimed at altering the subjective beliefs that the audience holds towards a particular political issue or policy. Therefore, structuring arguments and discourse worthy of the public's beliefs is critical to persuasion. In other words, mastering the use of rhetorical strategies is crucial to meet the goals or interests of political figures when tackling political issues. In the bulk of the literature, few studies have been undertaken via the application of the three Aristotelian rhetorical strategies: ethos, pathos, and logos to shed light on political discourse. Corax and Tisias were the first to define rhetoric as the "artificer of persuasion" (Lin, 2000). Aristotle considers rhetoric as a discipline, describing it as the art and power of discovering the best among all available means of persuasion. So the art of rhetoric is characterized as the use of linguistic resources to persuade others through the employment of the organization and style of language to shape attitudes and actions on the audience. Differently worded, it is the use of language, power relations, signs, and logic to impose order on reality, to alter perspectives, preferences and attitudes of an audience towards a certain issue.

The second part of this section examines a number of case studies

Cherwitz and Zagacki 1986 found that some US presidents tend to use "consummatory" discourse, displaying anger towards enemies to make listeners feel like their frustration is shared, and justificatory discourse, justifying military intervention during crises involving other nations. While these may be the strategies that are used, they may make listeners more upset during a crisis rather than keeping them calm. The "consummatory" strategy can perpetuate hatred toward perceived enemies and justifying military action can make people more eager to fight (Cherwitz & Zagacki, 1986). FDR seemed to have the opposite goals during the Great Depression, which is why he is a good subject to study to learn how to calm listeners rather than making them angrier. Donato (2009) examined Bush and Obama's rhetoric in the 2008 Recession. Bush started by avoiding admitting that there was a major problem, but it was not successful (Donato, 2009). Obama initially used blaming rhetoric (Ibid.). While he was very popular at the beginning of his presidency because of his policies, his crisis rhetoric was not very successful (Ibid.). FDR could not have possibly been successful trying to make the Great Depression sound less drastic with the Bush approach, and there was not a clear group to blame as in the Obama approach,

though many were already blaming Hoover. FDR was forced to use a different kind of rhetoric.

Hashim (2015) investigated the role of language in the communication and interpretation of intentions by examining selected political speeches of John Kerry in Presidential Campaign in 2004 and George Bush Inaugural address in 2001 since they have the same purposes as pieces of discourse with specific goals. Hence, the study focused on the pragmatic functions of locution, illocutionary and perlocutionary acts of the speeches.

Mshvenieradze (2013) explored the strategies of Aristotelian rhetoric (i.e., logos, ethos, and pathos) used by the candidates, Jacques Chirac and Nicolas Sarkozy, during the French presidential elections in 2002 and 2007. In this study, it was found that these two candidates employed logos, ethos, and pathos in their political discourse with some differences. Nicolas Sarkozy tended to draw comparisons and use stylistic techniques that evoked the audience's emotion, while Jacques Chirac emphasized values and repetitively used phrases to appeal to the audience's emotion. Additionally, both candidates established their ethos by utilizing personal and possessive pronouns. Similarly, Jay (2006) applied Aristotle's rhetoric to the speeches of two North American Native leaders, Tecumseh and Pushmataha. It was found that the utilization of ethos, logos, and pathos, as well as enthymemes and examples between these two leaders in their discourse was very resembling. This was particularly evident by the similarity in structures, proofs, and topics adopted by both Tecumseh and Pushmataha. He further concluded that "Aristotle's theories defy time and place; they are work, which explains the continuing interest in his observations of the art of rhetoric" (Jay, 2006, p. 114). Additionally, Bronstein (2013), using Aristotelian rhetoric, analysed the Facebook pages of the 2012 U.S. presidential candidates. The findings revealed that both Obama and Romney used emotional appeal to create social investments towards their campaign. Moreover, pathos was the most pervasive element utilized in both candidates' Facebook pages, while logos was the least prevalent strategy used. An impressive finding in this study is that both candidates used pathos to appeal to the audience's emotions in an attempt to discourage discord and encourage effective alliances.

In the context of the Russia-Ukraine war, a number of studies have examined the discourse of Russian and Ukrainian politicians and leaders. Kruglov and Ivanenko (2016) conducted a study analysing Putin's speeches regarding the Ukrainian crisis, focusing on the concepts of "we" and "they" in his discourse. The study found that Putin's use of these pronouns aimed to create a sense of unity among Russians while emphasizing the differences between Russians and Ukrainians. This study's objective is aligned with Kruglov and Ivanenko's research as it also seeks to analyse Putin's discourse practices during the Russia-Ukraine war. It pushes the reflection on Putin's and Zelensky's use of 'we' versus 'they' to the use of other persuasive strategies.

These empirical studies contribute to the growing body of literature on Critical Discourse Analysis and Political Discourse. By applying a linguistic perspective to the speeches of Putin and Zelensky during the Russia-Ukraine war, this study aims to provide a

comparative analysis of their discourse and investigates how their language use contributes to the construction of narratives and the shaping of public opinion.

3. Methodology

This section focuses primarily on the manner in which the data of the study were collected and analysed. In this comparative study, the data were collected from the public speeches of Vladimir Putin and Volodymyr Zelensky during the war that opposes their respective countries. The data collection process was guided by a set of pre-determined criteria, such as the use of the personal pronouns (“I” versus “you”, “we” versus “they”) and the use of persuasive strategies (pathos, logos, ethos), this explains the use of the purposive sampling technique to select speeches. After retaining two speeches from each of the two presidents, the first step of the analysis which involved segmenting the texts into meaningful discourse units was used. Discourse units were then coded using thematic analysis which enabled the identification of patterns and themes in the data. These were useful in identifying the dominant discourse strategies used by the two Presidents during the war. The analysis was done following Fairclough’s Critical Discourse Analysis and Aristotle’s persuasive techniques. Tables and percentages were used for visibility purposes.

4. Analysis and Discussion

In this section, the speeches used are indicated and categorized on tables. Then, the linguistic and other persuasive strategies used are also presented.

4.1 Speeches Used

The two speeches of Vladimir Putin are:

- Russian President Vladimir Putin said at Moscow’s Red Square Victory Day parade that the world was at a “turning point” and claimed a “war” had been unleashed against Russia. Read the transcript here. Putin Delivers Victory Day Speech. May 9, 2023
- Speaking during an emergency televised address in Moscow on Saturday, President Vladimir Putin has promised that he would not allow Russia to slip into civil war, after Yevgeny Prigozhin, the leader of the Wagner mercenary force, seized a key military headquarters overseeing the offensive in Ukraine. 24 Jun 2023

The two speeches of Volodymyr Zelensky selected are:

- Russia-Ukraine crisis: Zelensky’s address in full, 24 Feb 2022. Hours before Russia invaded his country, Zelensky made a powerful speech. This is what he said.
- ‘Thirteen days of struggle’: Zelensky’s speech to UK parliament – transcript Ukrainian president delivers historic address to MPs in the Commons via video link as country resists Russian invasion. Tue 8 Mar 2022.

Table 1. Information on the collected speeches of Putin and Zelensky

Author	Title of speech	Date	Place	Transcript by
Vladimir Putin	Victory Day Speech	May 9, 2023	Moscow's Red Square	Al Jazeera and news agencies
Vladimir Putin	Russia will not slip into a civil war	24 Jun 2023	Moscow	Al Jazeera and news agencies
Volodymyr Zelensky	Address to the nation	24 Feb 2022	Kiev	Al Jazeera and news agencies
Volodymyr Zelensky	Zelensky's speech to UK parliament	Tue 8 Mar 2022	House of Commons via video link	Parliament TV, UK

4.2 Use of the Pronouns "they" and "we", "their" and "our", etc.

In order to create their various identities, both leaders regularly made use of personal pronouns. This is displayed on the table below.

Table 2. Some instances of the use of pronouns by the two leaders

Author/Speech	Instances	Context of use and implication
P 1 (a)	the day of <i>our</i> great victory.	Celebrating victory together, not by him alone
P1 (b)	where <i>we</i> remember those	Russians
P1 (c)	their lives for <i>our</i> country in	Pride of fatherland
P1 (d)	what <i>we</i> want for the future	All of us Russians and not "I", Putin alone
P1 (e)	<i>they</i> keep talking of <i>their</i> exceptionalism	Distancing Russians from the so-called western exceptionalism
P1 (f)	<i>They</i> are the ones destroying family values, traditional values	Not us Russians
P1 (g)	And <i>you</i> , current soldiers, <i>you</i> are worthy. <i>You</i> are fighting for <i>your</i> friends, for <i>your</i> loved ones, for <i>your</i> family	He repeatedly uses you and your to give credit to the Russians who are defending their fatherland

P1 (h)	All of <i>you</i> who are serving <i>your</i> nation as part of the great patriotic war.	He repeatedly uses you and your to give credit to the Russians who are defending their fatherland
P2 (a)	Directed against <i>us</i> is the whole military, economical and information machines of the West.	...us, including "I" Putin. We are all therefore in danger
P2 (b)	, the actions splitting <i>our</i> unity are a betrayal of <i>our</i> people, of <i>our</i> brothers in combat	This is a great show of patriotism and of national feelings
P2 (c)	<i>We</i> will not let this happen again. <i>We</i> will protect our people	All Russians are involved in the protection of their country
Z1 (a)	common border is dividing <i>us</i>	Russians as against Ukrainians
Z1 (b)	<i>We</i> know for sure that <i>we</i> don't need the war	Both Russians and Ukrainians don't need the war (note the conciliatory tone)
Z1 (c)	if they try to take <i>our</i> country away from <i>us</i> , our freedom, <i>our</i> lives, the lives of <i>our</i> children, <i>we</i> will defend ourselves	Indication of inclusiveness and patriotism
Z2 (a)	the war that <i>we</i> didn't start and <i>we</i> didn't want.	We the peace-loving people of Ukraine
Z2 (b)	However <i>we</i> have to conduct this war, <i>we</i> do not want to lose what <i>we</i> have, what is <i>ours</i> , <i>our</i> country Ukraine	Showcasing the bravery of the Ukrainians
Z2 (c)	<i>Our</i> army showed <i>us</i> who we are."	Being proud of the Ukrainian army
Z2 (d)	<i>They</i> do not allow any food	The vicious Russian army

Note. Examples are drawn from the speeches under study annotated as follows: P1= Putin's speech 1, P2= Putin's speech 2, Z1= Zelensky's speech 1, Z2= Zelensky's speech 2

Both leaders make great use of pronouns to show their attachment and their patriotism. Elsewhere they use pronouns to vilify their opponents. The tokens P1(a), P1(b), P1(c) and P1(d) are evident in the following excerpt:

People of Russia, veterans of Russia, comrades, soldiers, quartermasters, officers of the Army, the Navy, the Air Force, admirals, generals, commanders in chief of the special military operations, I salute you all. I salute you all on today to mark the day of *our* great victory. Today is a day where *we* remember those who came before us, those who fell on the battlefield and in doing so became immortals, who joined the regiment of immortals, who gave up their lives for *our* country in the fight against Nazism. And that fight is one which is rearing its head again today. Once again, *we* see war that is afoot, but *we* have been pushing back, fighting against international terrorism to protect the people in the Donbas region and to protect our country.

Token P1(a) says, "...mark the day of *our* great victory." Here, we see a leader who is conscious of collective victory. Remember that he addresses all the compartments of the military, veterans of Russia, quartermasters, and indeed the entire people of Russia. He does not attribute the victory to his exceptional bravery but to everyone. P1(c) heightens the notion of patriotism and concerted effort. P1(d) which goes thus, "...what *we* want for the future" simply enjoins all Russians and not Putin alone. He kind of recuses himself from the actions on the field which ironically he is masterminding.

It is interesting to note the way he uses the pronouns "they" and "their" as portrayed in the paragraph that follows:

Our only friendships that we can have between the east and west around this world, what we want for the future is a future of peace, a future of stability, not a future of blood. But the elite in the west, *they* keep talking of *their* exceptionalism, of how *they* are different, and *they* are the ones creating a sense of disruption between our people. *They* are the ones destroying family values, traditional values that make everyone on this planet human. *They* are forcing *their* will on other nations, forcing *their* rules on others. But it would appear that *they* have forgotten what Nazism was all about.

The essence of the use of tokens P1(e) and P1(f), all demonstrated in the above paragraph, is to distance Russians from the so-called "western exceptionalism". He is telling Russians that countries of the west have their own culture and traditions which they want to impose on them. The probable message is that all Russians should stand up as one man and resist what he would most likely western imperialism.

The next set of pronouns used by Putin are “you” and “your”, evident in the paragraph that follows:

We know what it means to fight for one’s country. And *you*, current soldiers, *you* are worthy. *You* are fighting for *your* friends, for *your* loved ones, for *your* family. And I know that *you* feel the great love that we have for *you*, that they have for *you*. Everyone, everyone is ready to support *you* and to give *you* any that *you* needed, any prayers that you need.

The pervasive use of the pronouns “you” and “your” () is a deliberate effort by Putin to recognize the effort of the Russian soldiers and to give them the credit for whatever successes they might have registered this far. He even says that he and the rest of the civilian Russians love them because of their bravery. With this kind of encouraging words, the soldiers have no option but to continue to fight, even at the expense of their lives.

Zelensky uses “us” and “we” in Z1(a) and Z1(b) in a more inclusive and conciliatory manner. The extract below portrays this:

More than 2,000km of the common border is dividing *us*.

We know for sure that we don’t need the war. Not a Cold War, not a hot war

The “us” in Z1(a) above refers to Russians as against Ukrainians. The “we” in Z1(b) refers to both the Russians and the Ukrainians. We notice here that the audience being addressed here is made up of Russians and Ukrainians and we remark the inclusive and peaceful approach used by Zelensky. This was probably he was not for war but rather for a peaceful resolution of the conflict.

In Z1(c) we see a turn of approach on the part of Zelensky. Consider the following paragraph:

But if *we*’ll be attacked by the [enemy] troops, if they try to take *our* country away from *us*, *our* freedom, *our* lives, the lives of *our* children, *we* will defend ourselves. Not attack, but defend ourselves. And when you will be attacking *us*, you will see *our* faces, not *our* backs, but *our* faces.

He assumes the position of a patriot, somebody who is ready to fight alongside his people even if it means to die in the course. The impact of his use of these pronouns in this context is soul-touching. We can observe how the Ukrainians, though aware of their numerical and even military strength, still believe in their leader and holding tight to the fight.

Like Putin, Zelensky uses “our” in Z2 to showcase the bravery of the Ukrainian soldiers. He says:

“The next day, the artillery started fighting *us*. *Our* army showed *us* who *we* are.”

In other words, he intimates that “we could resist and fight the occupying forces”. Pronouns like these certainly go to boost the morale of the Ukrainian soldiers.

The “they” in Z2(d) is used to show how villainous the Russian army is. They go up to blocking food supplies to the Ukrainians. He says:

“On day 13, in the city of Mariupol that was attacked by the Russian force, a child was killed. They do not allow any food, any water and people started panicking”.

From the above analysis, we notice that both leaders make use of pronouns to create and reinforce certain ideologies such as otherness and villainy (they, their,), bravery and patriotism (our, us, your). We however note that Zelensky uses the pronouns “we” and “us” in a unique manner. He uses them for conciliatory purposes and also to show inclusiveness.

The use of the pronouns “we” versus “they”, “our” versus “their”, us versus “them”, etc. by Vladimir Putin and Volodymyr Zelensky is in line with the results of previous researches. Billig (2005), for example, says that “The use of “We” vs. “They” is a prevalent linguistic strategy employed in political discourse to create a sense of belonging among the in-group and to establish a sense of otherness or difference regarding the out-group (Billig, 1995). This linguistic strategy aims to foster an “us vs. them” mentality, where the “We” represents the group to which individuals belong, and the “They” represents those who are perceived as outsiders.

Similarly, Chilton (2004) posits that “In political conflicts, the use of “We” vs. “They” becomes particularly significant as it contributes to the construction of national identities and power dynamics. Political leaders strategically employ this linguistic strategy to mobilize support, consolidate their in-group, and foster a sense of collective identity (Chilton, 2004). By framing the conflict as a battle between “We” vs “They” leaders seek to create a strong sense of solidarity and loyalty among their supporters while simultaneously vilifying the opposing side (Van Dijk, 2009).

4.3 The Use of Persuasive Techniques

The analysis in this section will be based on Aristotle’s (1939) persuasion appeals (Ethos, Logos, and Pathos). Aristotle notes that three elements enter into the ability to persuade: (1) the speaker's character (ethos), (2) the audience's emotions (pathos), and (3) the rationality of the speech's arguments (logos) (Beiner 1983, p. 87). Persuasive speech must present the right impression of the speaker's character, work on the

audience's emotions, and prove the truth of the statements made. The researcher read through the speeches under study and identified instances of ethos, logos, and pathos. They were then categorized and discussed.

Table 5. *Persuasive Strategies in Putin's and Zelensky's Speeches*

Persuasive strategies	Vladimir Putin	Volodymyr Zelensky	Total
Ethos	7	5	12
Pathos	4	12	16
Logos	8	7	15
Total	19	24	43

A keen look at table 5 indicates that both Putin and Zelensky constantly try to provide reasons and explanations as to why they are taking the decisions they are taking. Let us consider these two examples from both Putin and Zelensky.

Their impunity is a great tragedy, and that is the very reason why today Ukrainian people are being held hostage. They're being held hostage following a coup, and they are just puppets in a game that is being played by the west. (P1)

Do Russians want the war? I would like to know the answer. But the answer depends only on you, citizens of the Russian Federation. (Z1)

In (P1), we see Putin providing reasons why Russia should stand firm and not to succumb to the machinations of the west. Putin further seems to be explaining to his countrymen that Ukraine as a country is not necessarily the problem but that they are a puppet of the west and must be combatted. The second example (Z1), demonstrates how Zelensky uses the rhetorical approach to appeal to the consciences of Russians who should, according to him, bring pressure to bear on their government not to go to war against them.

Furthermore, both Putin and Zelensky carefully establish their authority over their various audiences as can be seen in the examples that follow:

I spoke to the commanders in all directions last night. I appeal also to those who were deceptively pulled into the criminal adventure, pushed towards a serious crime of an armed mutiny (P1).

Today I initiated a phone call with the president of the Russian Federation. The result was silence. Though the silence should be in Donbas. That's why I want to address today the people of Russia. I am addressing you not as a president, I am addressing you as a citizen of Ukraine (Z1)

In (P1), Putin addresses his compatriots in an emergency televised addresses in which he assures the nation that he is in close contact with all the commanders of the army who have to double their vigilance with respect to the anti-patriotic activities of the Wagner group. In June 2023, the Wagner mercenaries seized a key military headquarters

overseeing the offensive in Ukraine. This was seen as an attempt to destabilize the country. Putin therefore had to come out powerfully to reassure Russians that everything is under control.

We see in (Z1) that, in order to be more credible to the Russian people, he (Zelensky) had to assume the position, not of a president, but of an ordinary citizen talking to other citizens.

The use of pathos was also demonstrated as in the excerpts that follow:

They are the ones destroying family values, traditional values that make everyone on this planet human. They are forcing their will on other nations, forcing their rules on others. But it would appear that they have forgotten what Nazism was all about (P1)

We know for sure that we don't need the war. Not a Cold War, not a hot war. Not a hybrid one. But if we'll be attacked by the [enemy] troops, if they try to take our country away from us, our freedom, our lives, the lives of our children, we will defend ourselves. Not attack, but defend ourselves. And when you will be attacking us, you will see our faces, not our backs, but our faces (Z1)

Example P1 above is an emotional appeal to the Russians to see the danger of their family values and culture being adulterated. This particular appeal leads the Russians to believe that his (Putin) actions against Ukraine and the west are justified.

In the example (Z1) above, Zelensky appeals to the emotions of the Russians he is addressing by conceding indirectly that though they are the weaker ones; though they are smaller in number and military might, if his country is attacked, *"we will defend ourselves. Not attack, but defend ourselves. And when you will be attacking us, you will see our faces, not our backs, but **our** faces."*

5. Conclusion

The aim of this study was to conduct a comparative analysis of selected speeches delivered by Russian President Vladimir Putin and Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelensky during the Russo-Ukrainian war. The study employed two theories for its analysis. They are Fairclough's Critical Discourse Analysis and Aristotle's persuasive strategies of Ethos, Logos and Pathos. The findings portray that both Vladimir Putin and Volodymyr Zelensky use pronouns and other linguistic choices to show otherness, bravery, patriotism and togetherness. However, Zelensky uses the pronouns "we" and "us" to portray his willingness in the peaceful resolution of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine. The two leaders also make use of different kinds of appeals in their speeches.

While Vladimir Putin relies more on logical appeals, Volodymyr Zelensky resorts more to emotional appeals through the use of pathos.

6. References

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